

LGBTQ MOVEMENT IN INDIA: A POST-CIVIL SOCIETY RESISTANCE?

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ABSTRACT

Identity is one of the key variables in a society that makes differences among people or groups. No particular identity is accepted wholeheartedly by all associated with human society. Some always play a dominant role over another. Since no identity is accepted by all and some identities play a dominant role, so it is implied that some identities take position at the centre of the society and some other are at the margin. This characteristic exists in human society from the very beginning. The LGBTQ community in India has been facing this type of problem due to their sexual and/or gender identity which is 'beyond normative' to the 'homophobic' state as well as to the society. Several dimensions are associated with the deprivation of LGBTQ people in India due to their which need to be explored. This article also offers a critique on liberal democratic state which, in practice, to large extent promotes a 'majoritarian normative' version of democracy. Civil society also shows its limits to transform its theory into actual practice. This article, finally, intends to draw a question whether can the LGBTQ movement be regarded as a post-civil society resistance or not.

Key words: LGBTQ, homonormativity, heteronormativity, 'majoritarian normativism', democracy, post-civil society.

FOREWORD:

It is a known fact now that Politics is no longer confined only to the domain of the state structures or institutions, but it includes various social phenomena within its rich domain. Political actions and social issues are intricately related with each other. Social actions tend to determine the political actions and vice versa. The study of power and politics, therefore, needs to be analyzed in a larger arena of complementary relationship between ‘political’ and ‘social’. For instance, identity is predominantly a matter of society, but different positions of different identities in a society might lead to power inequalities, and hence power struggles. Therefore, it becomes a matter of politics since politics is essentially a struggle for power. Similarly, the role of the state is imperative to restore social position of a particular identity. The LGBTQ people in India are confronting this type of identity based power discourse because of their sexuality which is ‘non-normative’ to the ‘homophobic’ state as well as to the dominant section of the society.

The process of ‘othering’ sometimes triumphs without facing minimal resistance while sometimes lead to confrontation and power based identity conflict. The more differences of identity, the more possibility of politics of identity because difference and othering are related to the power discourse. Foucault (1977) contributed a significant notion about the relation between discourse and power. Discourse means an influential stance to define something, describe something and narrate something. Power has a key role to construct a particular discourse. Power discourse always tends to customize its reason or rationality. Some people constantly intend to perpetuate their discourse and

exclude the rest who are the deviant from formers' reason, rationality and standard; therefore the 'other' takes place. Foucauldian notion of power discourse unveils the way to how discourses of power are exercised in all societies to marginalize the 'deviant' people or group. Nevertheless, social othering is, perhaps, unescapable in all societies at all-time, but the concept of 'othering' has been popularized after the emergence of postmodernism and postcolonialism. Postmodernism unveiled how discourses of power define people and impute a particular identity; on the other hand, 'postcolonialism claims the rights of all people on the earth to the same material and cultural well-being' (Young, 2003: 2).

LGBT QUEER IDENTITY:

The term 'queer' is much relevant in this argument. Queer means beyond or deviating from the usual or expected. The word 'queer' is used both as a noun and as an adjective or even as a verb. As a noun or adjective, 'queer' is a 'pejorative' term for denoting 'particular subject' and reflects on 'what it means to be a queer' (Leckey and Brooks, 2010: 2). It directly signifies 'homosexual' people (Glover and Kaplan, 2009: 114) or those who practice homosexuality or lesbianism or bisexuality, and it is against of the 'normal' mode of heterosexuality (Menon, 2005: 33-40). As a verb 'queer' denotes 'to spoil' or 'to put out of order' (Glover and Kaplan, 2009: 114) or 'its outlaw work' (Leckey and Brooks, 2010: 2). Then queer as a verb referring to rejection of the sacrosanct values of sexual purity. So, the term 'queer' is used for describing the homosexual people or the LGBT (lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender) community as well as their activities relating to sex which are beyond 'sexual normativity'. Queer

lesbian identity, in Indian context, is depicted remarkably in the film *Fire* (1996) made by Deepa Mehta. *Fire*, a story of two women, Radha and Sita, who tried to depart from traditional patriarchal values of sexuality to women who struggle to be empowered to choose their own notion of sexuality which is somehow outside of tradition and they accepted homosexuality. Then here, queer identity is supposed as from submissive, sexually pure women to the sexually impure. This film exhibited that there is an enduring inclination of society to symbolize men/women both by imagining them as to be sexually pure. This film reveals that homosexuality, contrary to the Indian culture, can extensively be regarded as a 'foreign Western import and imposition; it is considered to be the product of a corrupt culture rather than a biological disposition' (Burton, 2013). Then homosexuality, according to the chauvinists, is a rejection of the sacrosanct values of sexual purity.

Though the term LGBT is often loosely used to refer to homosexual people, but LGBT is an umbrella term comprises many categories, viz. lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender, transsexual, intersexual, and most importantly, men who have sex with men (henceforth referred to as MSM). Before explaining different types under the umbrella term LGBT, it would be better to explain first the differences between sex and gender. Sex is a biological disposition, unalterable and based on the natural inequalities (man and woman), while gender is a social construction, alterable and based on the conventional inequalities (masculine and feminine) customized by the society. Lesbian, gay and bisexual people are clearly concerned with their sexuality – lesbian means a female who is sexually attracted to another female or homosexual female; gay refers to a male who is sexually attracted to another male or homosexual male; and

‘bisexual’ refers to those person who are attracted to both male and female. Now the differences between transsexual and transgender need to be explained. People who are transsexual feel emotionally and psychologically that they were born with a wrong sex. Their assigned sexual identity is not the same with their sexual desire or orientation. They intend to go for surgery and/or sex reassignment therapy for saturating their sexual needs. On the other side, transgender is a multifaceted term, usually referring to a person who feels that his/her in gender behaviour, culture or outfit referring to sex is not conforming to his/her masculine/feminine gender identity prescribed by the society concerned. Transgender people, unlike transsexual, do not intend to alter their sex by surgery and/or sex reassignment therapy. Another category of the LGBT umbrella community is intersex means those who do not fit with male or female in terms of their reproductive organ. Sometimes the *hijra* people are considered as transgender and sometimes as intersex. *Hijras*, ‘as neither men nor women, function as an institutionalized third gender role’ [due to] ‘their ambiguous sexual nature’ [and] ‘as an institutionalized third gender role, the *hijras* are of interest not only in themselves, but also for their significance to the study of gender categories and human sexual variation’(Nanda, 1999: ix). *Hijra* denotes both *eunuch* which refers to an ‘emasculated male’ and *hermaphrodite* which refers to ‘a person whose genitals are ambiguously male-like at birth. When this is discovered, the child, previously assigned to the male sex, would be recategorized as intersexed – as a *hijra*’ (Nanda, 1999: 14). However, transgender, transsexual and intersex people are considered to belong to the category of the Third gender or Third sex. Sometimes gay and MSM are treated as the same, but some differences can be drawn between the two categories. Gay people do not have necessarily sex with men, but MSM denotes sexual relations between men despite whatever their identity as gay or

non-gay. The term MSM is used in public health discussion especially in the case of HIV. Thus, LGBT people are ‘other’ of male-female sexual and masculine-feminine gender binary. In this way ‘by limiting gender to simply the definitions of “man” and “woman,” there is a wide range of identities that are excluded from the equation’ (Basiliere, 2011: 142). Even though, as stated earlier, the LGBT people are labeled as ‘queer’ for their deviant nature of sexual and gender identity. But, now the question is, why the LGBT people are queer! Is it only because their sexual identity and/or gender identity is not analogous with majority of the people of the human society? Because mental, physical and psychological desires of the LGBT people are not akin with the majority of the people? Because their sexuality is not productive? Because the LGBT ‘queer’ people are positioned outside the mainstream, and not centered in the decision making power structure? Probably, all answer would be yes in this discourse. At this juncture, homosexuality, perhaps, has to create a reverse discourse to be the ‘self’, to be the ‘centered’. Foucault had a credence about the reverse discourse of homosexuality: ‘...it also made possible the formation of a "reverse" discourse: homosexuality began to speak in its own behalf, to demand that its legitimacy or "naturalness" be acknowledged...’ (Foucault, 1976: 101).

Here two concepts, which are closely associated with the LGBT queer identity – heteronormativity and homonormativity, need to be discussed. Heteronormativity stands for normal and preferred sexual orientation, like sexual relation is ought to be made between opposite sexes – male and female. Homonormativity is a reverse conception of heteronormativity because it is in favour of homosexuality, nonetheless homonormativity does not promote

homosexuality as only preferred sexual orientation. Homonormativity is

‘a politics that does not contest dominant heteronormative assumptions and institutions, but upholds and sustains them, while promising the possibility of a demobilized gay constituency and a privatized, depoliticized gay culture anchored in domesticity and consumption’ (Duggan, 2002: 179).

But, importantly, demands of all the constituent members of the LGBT community are not identical. For instance, lesbian or gay people are demanding same-sex marriage or right to homosexuality, but all lesbian or gay are not in favour of same-sex marriage. Some of the scholars advocated for not to legalize same sex marriage because ‘queer culture is oppositional to normative hetero-sexual culture, and that this distinct culture is at risk of dissolution when queer individuals gain the right to marriage’ [and] ‘the efforts to gain access to same-sex marriage fail to contest dominant heteronormative assumptions and institutions’ (Reczek and Rothblum, 2012: 465). Bisexual people are concerned about both homosexuality and heterosexuality while lesbian and gay people are looking for that time when homosexuality would be legalized by the State as a human right. On the other hand, intersex or *hijra* people are demanding their civil rights like social and economic security, abolition of discrimination they have been facing since antiquity; reservation in education and job; political rights, like right to elect and right to be elected. MSM people need special health care due to they are much prone to be affected by HIV. Thus, the LGBTQ community is not monolithic in nature.

ROUTES OF OTHERING:

Social othering is a type of social banishment with multidimensional *modus operandi* – social, economic, cultural and political. The LGBT queer people are socially outcasted due to social values nourished by them. The values fostered by the LGBT people are not normative contrary to the dominant entrenched values. Non-acceptance of the values of the LGBT people towards their life and society is virtually non-acceptance of their culture. The ‘queer’ identity of the LGBT community, which made them ‘other’, is a consequence of the European modernity and derived in India by the colonial invader. Process of othering of the LGBT community has been institutionalized and legitimized by Section 377 or "unnatural offences" of the Indian Penal Code (henceforth referred to as IPC) framed in 1860 by Lord Macaulay, the President of the then Indian Law Commission. According to the Section 377 of IPC,

‘Unnatural offences – Whoever voluntarily has carnal intercourse ‘against the order of nature’ with any man, woman or animal, shall be punished with imprisonment for life, or with imprisonment of either description for a term which may extend to ten years, and shall also be liable to fine. Explanation.— Penetration is sufficient to constitute the carnal intercourse necessary to the offence described in this section.’

By this very section of the IPC, homosexuality is ‘against the order of nature’ thus it is illicit as well as a punishable offence. Today, the law, many liberal studies scholars are of the opinion, is analyzed as the colonizer’s exertion to impose values of public morality of the Victorian era on the subjects of its largest colony

India, which has been fundamentally pluralist in nature. Modern nation-state produces a notion of understanding by which some standard norms can be provided for consuming rights for its citizens within a given territory of the State. In the diverse facets of people's existence and identity, like religion, gender, sexuality, caste, etc. based on 'hierarchy of privilege and denial' produces this politics of exclusion and try to create 'normative citizen' (Khanna, 2013). This is, somehow, an instance of what Gudavarthy (2013: 10) said, 'enactment of draconian laws in the name of preserving "law and order"'. This homophobic attitude can be seen from the notion of 'majoritarian versus minoritarian discourse'. Like majoritarian versus minoritarian discourse in terms of religion, caste, ethnicity, it would be treated as 'normative sexuality' versus 'non-normative sexuality'. This 'normativity' and/or 'non-normativity' are/is the exclusive production of the modern postcolonial nation-state for categorizing its citizens.

In a recent case study on LGBT in India, M. V. Lee Badgett (2014) has attracted our attention to some exclusionary dimensions:

- 41 percent of Indians do not want a homosexual neighbour, and 64 percent believe that homosexuality is not justified.
- Homosexual behaviour is regarded as a criminal offence in India, moreover there is not a single protective legislation in India for LGB people, and Transgender people in India have only recently been allowed the legal rights and recognition through a verdict of the Supreme Court.
- The LGBT people often undergo traumatic experience of violence, denial, and discernment in employment, education, health care, and access to social services. High rates of

poverty are pictured in several studies on the LGBT people in India.

- Public health studies provide a confirmation of health disparities due to social stigma and exclusion. The LGBT people are more prone to getting depressed, suicidal thinking, and affected by HIV than the general population.

In another report published in 2008, UNDP India has identified MSM as ‘vulnerable sexual minorities’ with very high prevalence rate to HIV (7.4 percent). The aforementioned report said that

‘The practice of male to male sexuality in India is very complex and in many ways, unique; MSM and Transgenders have emerged as a core high risk group in NACP-III. Decriminalization, although necessary, is not enough to combat homophobia and even in settings where some rights have been secured for MSM, they can easily be eroded. MSM interventions have thus to go hand in hand with fighting against stigma and discrimination and promoting human rights’ (UNDP, 2008).

Though right to homosexuality has been granted to the LGBT ‘queer’ people as a human right in many western countries, and United States has established herself as a global defender of LGBT ‘queer’ right by giving this right as human right, but this right has still remained unachieved in most of the postcolonial countries. For instance, homophobic or heterocentric attitude of postcolonial India is bared though there is a long tradition of democracy. Globally in more than 70 countries, resembling India, homosexuality is considered a crime. Some of these countries

impose fine or imprisonment like India (United Nations News Centre, 2010). It goes without saying that United Nations is in favour of decriminalization of homosexuality all over the world and this standpoint of United Nations has been substantiated by the statement of Ban Ki-moon, the former Secretary-General, as

‘Together, we seek the repeal of laws that criminalize homosexuality, that permit discrimination on the basis of sexual orientation or gender identity, that encourage violence. When individuals are attacked, abused or imprisoned because of their sexual orientation, we must speak out. We cannot stand by. We cannot be silent’ (United Nations News Centre, 2010).

Even in article 16 of United Nations Universal Declaration of Human Rights stated that

‘(1) Men and women of full age, without any limitation due to race, nationality or religion, have the right to marry and to found a family. They are entitled to equal rights as to marriage, during marriage and at its dissolution’ (United Nations Organization, 1948).

Thus, the process of othering of the LGBT people in India, especially of transgender people, can be summarized as follows:

- **Social dimension:** Transgender people leave their home due to non-acceptance by their family. Many of them are compelled to leave school due to transphobic attitudinal mentality of the majority.
- **Cultural dimension:** The culture comprises ideas, customs, social behavior, beliefs, attitudes, etc., conserved by the LGBT people are deviated from what is expected by the society. So they treated as ‘queer’.

- **Economic dimension:** Early driven out from home results very poor economic condition of the transgender people. Stigma and harassment are very common if they get a job. These causes lead them to engage with begging, prostitution, and illegal activities for their livelihood.
- **Social security dimension:** Since MSM and transgender people take sex work or prostitution as their livelihood, so frequently they face violence from their client, police, law enforcement officers and others as well. The LGB people also face security problem owing to Section 377 of IPC.
- **Health security dimension:** MSM and transgender people are more prone to be affected by HIV than general people due to stigma and exclusion ‘from doctors and other health care professionals who refuse to treat them; schools who expel or segregate HIV-positive children or children with HIV-positive parents; orphanages and housing entities that reject HIV-positive children; and employers who discriminate based on the applicant’s HIV-positive status’ (Zaman, Chad, & Schneeweis, 2016).
- **State initiatives dimension:** The state policy is hardly available to address the problems of transgender people. There are no such legislations to define the discrimination towards transgender community unlike women and other oppressed section of the society.

RESISTANCE:

In India, the LGBT community has been trying to establish homonormativity through judicial mechanism since 2001. The Naz Foundation, an NGO working for the welfare and rehabilitation of people with the HIV, filed a Public Interest

Litigation (PIL) against National Capital Territory of Delhi (Naz Foundation vs. Govt. of NCT of Delhi, WP [Civil] No. 7455 of 2001) at the Delhi High Court challenging section 377 of IPC in 2001. Later, in 2006, the Naz Foundation filed a special leave petition before the Supreme Court of India demanding decriminalization of homosexuality by repealing section 377 of IPC. Significantly, Delhi High Court gave a verdict in 2009 stating some portions of this particular section of IPC are *ultra vires* in nature as it violates the fundamental rights mentioned in Indian Constitution. A number of appeals were filed in the Supreme Court of India against the verdict of Delhi High Court. Then, in 2012, Ministry of Home Affairs gave a note of dissent to the Supreme Court about Delhi High Court's verdict, but later, surprisingly, the Central Government changed its stand on the said issue and supported decriminalization of homosexuality. The Central Government has been reprimanded by the apex court for its capricious attitude. Finally, in December 2013, the Supreme Court of India *set aside* the Delhi High Court's verdict. The apex court told that the Parliament should debate and decide on this issue. Some LGBTQ activists called the verdict of Supreme Court as 'loss for every citizen' since it is against 'fundamental rights of all citizens to sexuality, to dignity, to a right against violence and discrimination' (Khanna, 2013) because, firstly, the Delhi High Court verdict had granted 'right to sexuality' to everyone, not merely to the LGBTQ people; and secondly, the Delhi High Court judgement was path breaking since it had reflected 'constitutional morality' of Indian nation-state to provide equal dignity to all its citizens. Recently Madras High Court has asked the centre

'When more than 30 countries, including a conservative nation like Ireland, have decriminalized homosexuality and legalized gay marriage by way of referendum, getting 62.07% votes in favour, why not

India decriminalize homosexuality?’ (The Times of India, January 31st 2016).

Of late the Supreme Court of India said on 2nd February 2016 that, it will review this colonial-era law regarding homosexuality. So, after many phases of war in Delhi High Court and in Supreme Court of India, section 377 of IPC is continuing with its strength unabated. Besides these legal steps, the LGBT queer people are demanding their rights in a diverse manner from societal level. Several gay ‘pride parades’ have been organized in several cities, like Bengaluru, Delhi, Indore, Kolkata, Puducherry, Bhubaneswar and Chennai. Akhil Katyal describes Delhi Pride Parade as not only for the LGBT but for all because:

‘In India, LGBT politics has not come to this [USA form of civil rights movement] form, not yet, but strong signs of it are there and we have to resist them with all our might. In the Delhi Queer Pride this year, we march as individuals, holding in our hands the promise of a world in which LGBT politics runs with a larger progressive mandate and ties up with a larger version of equality for all’ (Katyal, 2014).

One LGBT magazine and one gay magazine, namely ‘Pink Pages’ and ‘Bombay Dost’ continue to be published since 2009. Some LGBT films have been exhibited in Mumbai Pride festivals in 2010 and 2011. In Madurai first LGBT Queer Rainbow Festival was held in 2012 with demanding to eradicate social discriminations faced by the LGBT people. In recent times, LGBT movement, one variant of New Social Movements, led by ‘homoprotectionist’ people have engrossed attention of the intelligentsia from India and abroad. After the 2013 verdict of the apex court of India, the LGBT community started to protest more in a systematic way by organizing several Pride Parades. In this

way, they have been able to collect limited support from some celebrities, Media and common people. These legal and social initiatives, taken by the LGBT people along with supporters, substantiated the observation ‘where there is power, there is resistance’ (Foucault, 1976: 95). This is, undoubtedly, an endeavor to establish a ‘counter-hegemony’ from homonormativity against the ‘hegemonic heteronormativity’.

CONCLUSION: IS IT A POST-CIVIL SOCIETY RESISTANCE?

This is akin to a satire that homosexuality has already been decriminalized in United Kingdom (UK) by the ‘Sexual Offences Act 1967’ (England and Wales), ‘Criminal Justice (Scotland) Act 1980’ and ‘Homosexual Offences (Northern Ireland) Order 1982’ respectively, but the same is ‘against the order of nature’ and a criminal offence in India by the section 377 of IPC made by the colonial British rulers (Debnath, 2017). United States, on the other hand, legalized nationwide same-sex marriage as human right in 2015, though there are also societal unfriendliness towards LGBTQ community. Human Rights Campaign (HRC), the largest LGBT civil rights support group and political lobbying organization in US, fights for LGBTQ for a considerable period with their huge support base from civil society. ‘Don't ask, don't tell’ policy in US military service is also repealed in September 2011. In this context, the ‘liberal’ democratic India¹, however, is not beyond question since the liberal discourse, theoretically, is deep-rooted in the sovereign authority of the individuals with their socio-political rights, right to property and right to freedom. The LGBTQ people are not entitled to avail these rights and it indicates the limits of the liberal democratic state (Debnath, 2017). If the liberal democratic state does not ensure the demands

of the ‘other’ then the liberal democracy turns into what J.S. Mill (1859) described as ‘tyranny of the majority’². In fact, most of the ‘so-called’ egalitarian, libertarian and utilitarian states have failed to accept the ‘other’. Liberal democracy and civil society are knottily linked to each other since ‘only a democratic state can create a democratic civil society and only a democratic civil society can sustain a democratic state’ (Walzer, 2007: 130). The ends of civil society, which are some ‘normative ideals’, are ‘to preserve democracy and expand the process of democratization’ (Gudavarthy, 2013: 1). But in this particular LGBTQ case, liberal democracy displays its limits because it focuses on ‘mobilization of power’ rather than its elimination, on one hand; and civil society also does not justify what the theory of civil society promises, on the other. Civil society is to ensure ‘protection as well as the enlargement of the basic civil liberties of the citizens’ (Gudavarthy, 2013: 34) and ‘it promises in theory – freedom from domination, freedom to achieve self-realization, freedom to assert selfhood’ (Chandhoke, 2003: 27). But, in practice, two problems are there related to the LGBTQ case: mass mobilization has not taken place due to ‘stigmatization’ of their culture; and there some sort of ‘ghettoization’³ has been congealed – only LGBTQ people speak for LGBTQ, and they are ‘self-enclosed cultural’ group. Nonetheless, some NGOs like Naz Foundation, Humsafar Trust, Sappho, etc., are battling for LGBTQ people, but these are contained in very small circle. NGO is only a part of civil society, not the whole. The NGOs work for LGBTQ in India got limited support from the larger society as well as from the political parties as queerness works negatively in ‘psyche’ of most of the people. An example from the UK Parliament might be interesting in order to understand the role of political parties for inclusion of LGBTQ people in decision making process. In General Election 2017, 45 MPs were elected in the UK Parliament from the LGBTQ community. Out of 45 members, 19 from both

Conservative and Labour Party, and 7 from Scottish National Party (Batchelor, 2017). The civil space in existing Indian democracy extends restricted possibilities for re-appropriation of the civil society for those who are outside the politically and economically organized sectors. Thus, civil society in India is both ‘exclusive and exclusionary’ in nature (Chandhoke, 2003). Then this LGBTQ movement is not for all in two senses – LGBTQ people are beyond or post-normative, though Katyal says that the LGBTQ movement looks for ‘a larger version of equality for all’; and intersectionality in society due to variety of demands within it, on the other hand. Therefore, demands of the ‘non-civil’ LGBTQ people is not granted as the civil rights. But, still, there is a hope, at least in theory, that civil society will manage the process of democratization while democracy, in practice, itself upholds some political as well as social ‘majoritarian normativism’. Then, the contemporary practices of civil society, whatever in its theory, do not able to manage the problems of the LGBTQ community through deliberation and bargaining with the state, so that is why the LGBTQ movement needs to be seen as an alternative practice to extend democratization which is beyond or post-civil society.

¹ Here, I, primarily, accept India as a liberal democratic state at least in theoretical sense. While preamble of the Indian constitution upholds India as a secular democratic republic state to promote justice, liberty and equality for all its citizens; a large numbers of fundamental rights have been incorporated in the constitution; universal adult franchise has also been granted in order to freely choose the representatives to govern the governed – then there is no way to deny that India is not a liberal democratic. Though some scholars may argue that this claim is controversial as India shows also some authoritarian stances in practice. Here, the ‘liberal’ nature of the Indian democracy is also challenged.

² The term ‘tyranny of the majority’, conceptualized by Alex de Tocqueville and later by John Stuart Mill, means the situation when the political and social

majority turns into a tyrant in a so called democratic state. Mill said, the social tyranny is more dangerous since it provides a least opportunity to be escaped and it penetrates more deeply into every parts of the life. See, John Stuart Mill, *On Liberty (1859)* (Kitchener: Batoche Books, 2011), pp. 8-9.

³ This concept is borrowed from Slavoj Zizek's concept of 'racism with a distance', conceptualized in his essay 'Multiculturalism, or, the Cultural Logic of Multinational Capitalism' (1997). 'Ghetto' is referring to the areas of Jewish people within European cities which are supposed to be kept 'quarantined' and physically separated due to their different culture. Thus 'ghettoization' means to restrict or to confine to a particular area or category. It implies a social isolation.

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